

Assessment of Fair Dealing and the Use of Mobile Phones to Access Subscribed Legal Information Resources by Law Students in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi

Raphael, Gabriel Okpologidi

Benue State University

rokpologidi@bsum.edu.ng; okpologidi@gmail.com

Sambe, Manasseh Tyungu CLN

Benue State Polytechnic Ugbokolo

sambemanasseh@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19071663>

Abstract

This study investigates fair dealing and the use of mobile phones to access information resources by law students in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi. The study employed descriptive research design. The population of the study was 83 law students who are duly registered with the Benue State University Law Library Makurdi in 2019/2020 academic session. Convenience sampling technique was employed. Data was collected through questionnaire and analyzed through descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages and mean. Results show that the library subscribed to e-library resources such as e-law books among others. Law students who are duly registered with the law library are allowed to utilize their mobile phones in the library to access subscribed law library resources. While majority of the law students used it to access other internet resources, e-newspapers and e-law books to a high extent, others used it to access e-law journals and e-law students' Long Essays, Dissertation and Theses to a less extent. A higher number of law students apply the concept of fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access, download and re-use subscribed information resources in the law library such as e-law journals among others and it has a greater impact on their educational achievement and research activities.

Keywords: Assessment, Fair dealing, mobile phones, access, information resources, law students, law library

Introduction

An academic law library is a specialized library or a reference library where specific information resources are made available for the use of those who study law or have an interest in the study of law. An academic law library is usually owned by Universities or an Institution Law Libraries like the ones found in law schools. It is a key requirement to have and operate a law library before an institution can gain accreditation to run a law programme (degree) in Nigeria. The academic library is expected to be housed within the Faculty or School of Law, and its collections are largely law-related.

Legal information resources are the fulcrum to professionalism in legal education and practices. The academic law library provides information resources for access and use at any time. These information resources should largely as identified by Raphael (2022) include statutes, law reports, journals and other periodicals. However, with the advent and application of information and communication technology, there is a drastic shift from the provision of print information resources in academic law library to digital or subscribed resources. This entails that the academic law library of the present time does not only provide the traditional print legal information resources but also provide electronic resources. This is gradually forcing the legal profession to attach more value on the electronic legal resources brought about by the modern technology.

Electronic information resources may therefore be regarded as digital resources that are processed for access and use of a target audience or users. These resources are called electronic legal information resources. This implies that, legal resources can be made available through any electronic device. Electronic resources, as identified by Adeniran (2013) usually consist of e-books, e-journal articles, newspapers, theses, dissertations, databases, and CD-ROMs, which are likely to be the alternative to the print media. These resources are either purchased and put on the

shelves or made available via subscription to electronic information resources via databases. The databases that contain electronic legal information resources are vital in enhancing users' access to the information required for effective and speedy use. As one of the emerging environments in libraries in general and the academic law libraries in particular, it facilitates information communication in the competitive service. Where these electronic resources are provided in form of databases, Law Students are allowed to explore and exploit these resources for their academic endeavours and pursuits. But, while using these resources, they must deal with the same fairly and within the ambits of the law. The essence of this study therefore is to assess how law students of the study area comply with the provisions of the law as it relates to the concept of fair dealing through the use of their mobile phones in accessing subscribed legal information resources.

Statement of the Problem

One of the greatest achievements in academic law libraries is the integration and use of mobile devices in the provision, access and use of electronic legal resources. The use of mobile devices by law students of the university is capable of facilitating easy access to subscribed legal resources and use.

Although, the Benue State University Makurdi conducts "GST 101: Use of library" as a general course with two units load to inculcate knowledge of the available library resources (print and electronic); the available devices or technologies for accessing and utilising the resources; as well as the use of information resources by law students in relation to copyright issues poses a challenge to be assessed. Consequently, it may be observed that law students of the university may not be effectively applying fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access and use subscribed law library resources in their academic endeavours. In spite of this, it has been observed that no empirical evidence has been found to the best

of the researchers' knowledge to investigate the extent of fair dealing application by law students in the use of mobile phones to access and use subscribed legal resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi. Thus, this creates a gap in the literature that this study is designed to bridge.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the fair dealing, extent to which law students use mobile phones to access subscribed legal information resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Identify various types of e-library resources subscribed by Benue State University Law Library Makurdi that are known to law students in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi.
2. Know if law students are allowed to use mobile phones to access subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi.
3. Determine the extent to which law students utilize mobile phones to access and use subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi
4. Determine the extent to which fair dealing is applied by law students in the use of mobile phones to access, download and re-use subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi
5. Determine the impact of fair dealing on law students use of mobile phones to access and use subscribed legal information resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the various types of e-library resources subscribed by Benue State

University Law Library Makurdi that are known to law students in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi

2. Are law students allowed to use mobile phones to access and use subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi?
3. To what extent do law students use mobile phones to access and use subscribed legal information resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi?
4. To what extent is fair dealing applied by law students in the use of mobile phones to access, download and re-use subscribed legal information resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi?
5. What is the impact of fair dealing on law students' use of mobile phones to access and use subscribed legal information resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi?

Literature Review

Although it has been asserted by Lord in Vosper (1972) that it is impossible to define what is "fair dealing", Asein (2017) opines that there is no clear definition of what fair dealing means in the first place, nor is there a consensus on the rules to be adopted in determining fair dealing under Nigerian law. Nonetheless, the term fair dealing could be described as a term that is used in the description of certain exceptions to exclusive rights provided under the law. For the purpose of this study, fair dealing is the extent to which a law student access, modify, and use electronic information resources while conducting a research or studying privately or reviewing or carrying out an assignment or writing long essay, dissertation, and thesis in fulfillment of the requirements for graduation and eligibility to be mobilised to the Nigerian Law School or awarded a postgraduate degree. There are three types of fair dealing. These are identified by

Sterling (1998) as where work is exploited for the purpose of research or private study, criticism or review, reporting current events, then such a work may be said to have being dealt with fairly.

Academic Law Library provides information resources such as statutes, law reports, journals and other periodicals. For the fact that much value is placed on print copies of these information resources in the legal profession, more emphasis is placed on the use of electronic information resources as encompassed in the law databases, as a result of the birth and application of information and communication technology. Bello (2018) identified these electronic information resources to include computer and computer systems, internet and intranet, electronic external storage devices such as CD, flash drives, etc., software packages, electronic books (e-books), and electronic serial publications such as e-journals. These electronic resources are subscribed by the academic law library for users' effective access and utilisation. However, efficient access and use of these resources by users (law students) via mobile phones or other electronic devices is *sine qua non* to achieving or attaining academic excellence. This is justified by Ogomodu and Ubiomini (2017) that the mobile phone applications have simplified the learning process and learning can take place at any time anywhere.

In order to effectively have access to electronic information resources for the purpose of learning or research in the law library, a user must legally be an owner or in lawful possession of such a said mobile phone or device. In most cases as part of library rules, these devices are not to serve as a distraction to the owner or possessor or be used as a means of disturbing other users of the library. It is trite that a user's right ends where another user's right begins. This accounts for why in most libraries; a band is placed on the use of mobile phones to make calls or watch videos in the library. Be that as it may, Raphael (2022) pointed out that students are allowed to use their

mobile phones for the purpose of exploring electronic information resources available in their libraries. Copyright holders are conferred by law with the monopolistic right of determining the extent and how their works may be explored or exploited. But in the interest of societal balance and development, certain exceptions are also created where permission or consent of the copyright holders is not required before such a work can be used. Fair dealing is one of such exceptions as provided by law. This largely falls under the exceptions created by various applicable copyright regimes. Raphael and Adaji (2024) further emphasizes while pointing out the significance of fair dealing that in Nigeria, Part II of the Copyright Act, 2022 provides for situations where literary, artistic, dramatic and musical works that are protected by copyright can be made available by Academic Libraries to be used (explored) by Library Users, without infringing on the monopolistic rights of the copyright holder. These situations include where the exploitation of the work is for the purposes of research, education, review, criticism, private use or parody, pitches, or caricature. These are known exceptions to the protection granted to copyright holders. But the question is, to what extent can libraries allow the exploitation of copyrightable information resources by staff and students who access them for the purposes of teaching, learning, and research? The extent is simply to deal fairly with these legal information resources within the bounds of the law.

Empirically, Okiki (2013) in his investigation of the availability of information resources' influence on academics' research productivity in Nigerian federal universities reveals that journals, books, the Internet, websites, search engines, e-journals, e-books, reference sources, and e-catalogues were readily available to academics. Chaputulu and Mulula (2018) in their study reveal that usage of mobile phones to access e-books, e-journals, and the library website was high. The use of these resources must, however, be seen to be fair and within the

bounds of the law. Gakibayo, Ikoja-Odongo and Okello-Obura (2013) also identified electronic information resources used in most libraries as CD-ROMS, e-books, e-databases, electronic journals, electronic current awareness services and information subject gateways accessed through the internet. The study of Zhang (1998) on the use of electronic resources by academic staff at Rollins College in the United States found that 69% of the academics sampled used the online catalogue, while 53% used UMI's ProQuest direct online databases and other online resources for their research activities. The use of electronic resources as found out by Adeniran (2013) has tremendous impact on the academic performances of the undergraduate students of Redeemer's University; however, there is need for them to acquire more skills in the use of electronic resources. Raphael, Tofi and Ojobo (2020) investigated the influence of Copyright Act 2004 on the provision of information resources in academic law libraries in North Central, Nigeria. Results reveal that Copyright Act has with it some attendant restrictions that makes it difficult for academic law libraries in North Central Nigeria to provide the desired information resources. The Act prevents piracy and reproduction of published works without prior consent of the owners. However, law information resources are expensive and especially original copies. Hence, the prevention of piracy by the Act in itself creates a problem of scarcity of information resources in academic law libraries as pirated copies tend to be cheaper with the same content as the original copy. This in turn affects the services provided in these libraries. The study finds that users of academic law libraries in North-Central Nigeria are aware of the relevant provisions of copyright Act, 2004 regarding the provision of information resource and that Sections of Copyright Act 2004 highly influence the provision of legal information resources in academic law libraries in North Central Nigeria. Also, in a similar research, Raphael, Tofi and Ojobo (2020) investigates the

perceived influence of Copyright Act, 2004 on the provision of information services in academic law libraries in North Central Nigeria. Results indicate that, the selected law libraries in the area are aware of the provisions of the Copyright Act, 2004 and the copyright Act 2004 has significant perceived influence on the provision of information services in the selected academic law libraries in the area. However, the findings indicate partial observance and enforcement of the provisions of the Act in these academic law libraries. This largely is as a result of lack of proper organisation of right owners in various aspects of intellectual property industry, lack of legal education on implications of intellectual property, lack of professional specialisation in the practice of intellectual property, globalisation and technology, dynamic nature of intellectual property, poor judicial sympathy and difficulty in negotiating licensing agreement for online databases.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population of the study was 83 law students who are duly registered with the Benue State University Law Library Makurdi in 2019/2020 academic session. Convenience sampling technique was employed to use the entire population of 84 as the study sample. This is because the population was small and therefore considered manageable. Data was collected through questionnaire and analysed through descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages and mean. The frequencies of respondents were used for the result of items 1-9, while mean was used for the result of items 10-29 with response options of VHE=Very High Extent; HE=High Extent; LE=Less Extent; NE=No Extent as well as SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree assigned with the weighing of 4, 3, 2, 1. The researchers considered the average mean of 3.25-4.00 as VHE/SA, 2.50-3.24 as HE/A, 1.75-2.49 as LE/D and 1.00-1.74 as NE/SD. Any mean of

2.50 and above was considered as accepted and used while any mean below 2.50 was rejected and not used.

Results

The results of this study is presented in tabular form and analyzed in line with the research objectives and questions that guide the study. To achieve this, a total number of 83 copies of questionnaires were distributed to respondents out of which 74 were retrieved and found usable

Table 1: The various types of e-library resources subscribed by Benue State University Law Library Makurdi that are known to law students in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi

S/N	Subscribed Library Resources that are known to law students	Subscribed	%	Not subscribed	%
1	e-Law books	62	83	11	14
2	e-Law journals	45	60	23	31
3	e-Newspapers	57	77	17	22
4	e-Magazines	64	81	10	13
5	e-Law students theses	41	55	33	44
6	e-Statutes	60	81	14	14
7	Internet resources	47	63	26	35

Table 1 presents various types of library resources subscribed by the BSU law library, Makurdi. It show that the law library subscribed to all the tabulated items with frequency and percentage ratings of 62 (83%), 64 (81%), 64 (81%), 57 (77%), 47 (63%), 45 (60%) and 41 (55%) respectively.

Table 2: Are Law students allowed to use mobile phones to access and use subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi

		N= 74			
S/N	Law students allowed to use mobile phones to access and use subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi	Yes	%	No	%
1	Are you allowed as a registered law student to use mobile phone to access subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi?	57	77	16	21
2	Are you allowed as a non-registered law library user though as a law student to use mobile phone to access subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi?	64	86	9	1

Table 2 presents, if law students are allowed to use of mobile phones to access subscribed library resources in BSU Law Library, Makurdi. It reveals that law students are allowed to use their mobile phones to access subscribed law library resources in BSU law Library, Makursi.

Table 3: Extent to which law students use mobile phones to access and use subscribed legal information resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi?

		N= 74					Decision
S/N	Extent to which law students use mobile phones to access and use subscribed legal	VHE	HE	LE	NE	X	Decision

information resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi							
1	Other Internet resources	17	23	12	11	3.5	VHE
2	e-Newspapers	34	29	6	4	3.3	VHE
3	e-Law books	36	12	17	8	3.0	VHE
4	e-Law journals	18	36	16	3	2.9	HE
5	e-Law students theses	36	16	10	11	2.7	HE
6	e-Statutes	24	12	17	10	2.4	LE
7	e-Magazines	14	17	24	18	1.7	NE

KEY: VHE=Very High Extent; HE=High Extent; LE=Less Extent; NE=No Extent

Table 3 presents the extent to which law students use mobile phones to access subscribed library resources in the BSU Law Library, Makurdi. It shows that law students use mobile phones to access subscribed library resources in BSU Law Library, Makurdi, such as other internet resources to a very great extent, with a mean rating of 3.5, while e-statutes and e-magazines with mean scores of 2.4 and 1.7, to no extent. All law students apply the concept of fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access subscribed library resources, such as e-statutes and e-magazines, to a great extent.

Table 4: Extent of Fair Dealing Applied by Law Students in the Use of Mobile Phones to Access, download, and Re-use Subscribed Library Resources

							N=	
							74	
S/N	Extent of applied concept of fair dealing by Law Students in the Use of Mobile Phones to Access, download, and Re-use Subscribed Library Resources	VHE	HE	LE	NE	<i>X</i>	Decision	
1	e-Law journals	29	30	9	5	3.1	HE	
2	e-Law books	35	21	10	7	3.1	HE	
3	e-Law students theses	44	10	10	9	3.0	HE	
4	e-Magazines	30	16	10	10	2.7	HE	
5	Other Internet resources	21	25	17	10	2.7	HE	
6	e-Statutes	14	32	10	17	2.4	LE	
7	e-Newspapers	28	10	10	21	2.3	LE	

KEY: VHE=Very High Extent; HE=High Extent; LE=Less Extent; NE=No Extent

Table 4 presents the extent to which the concept of fair dealing is applied by law students in the use of mobile phones to access, download, and re-use subscribed library resources in the BSU Law Library, Makurdi. It reported that while majority of the law students apply the concept of fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access, download and re-use subscribed library resources such as e-law journals, e-law books and e-law students' theses with mean scores of 3.1, 3.1 and 3.0 to a high extent, some apply it to a less extent with mean scores of 2.7, 2.7. However, others apply the concept to their access and use of e-statutes and e-newspapers, with mean scores of 2.4 and 2.3, respectively, to no extent.

Table 5: Law Students in the Use of Mobile Phones to Access, Download, and Re-use Subscribed Library Resources

N= 74

S/N	Law Students in the Use of Mobile Phones to Access, Download, and Re-use Subscribed Library Resources	SA	A	D	SD	X	Decision
24	Fair dealing enhances my educational achievement	40	16	14	3	3.3	SA
25	Fair dealing improves my research activities	29	37	4	3	3.3	SA
26	Fair dealing enables me to add value to the original word, line, or portion of the subscribed document I accessed through my phone	30	20	10	13	2.9	A
27	Fair dealing enables me to create new insights and understanding on words, lines or portions of the subscribed document accessed through my phone	18	32	14	9	2.8	A
28	Fair dealing prevents me from claiming ownership of other people's work	14	40	3	16	2.7	A
29	Fair dealing enhances my scholarship	13	30	13	10	2.4	D

KEY: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree

Table 5 presents the impact of the concept of fair dealing application on law students' use of mobile phones to access subscribed law resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi. It reveals that apart from item 29 with a mean score of 2.4, which is below the average point, items 24-28 are skewed to the affirmative, meaning that law students attested to the items with the mean scores of 3.3, 3.3, 2.9, 2.8, and 2.7, respectively.

Discussion of Finding

Results of this study are discussed based on the research question formulated to guide the study. It reveals that the subscribed known e-library resources among law students are e-law books, e-statutes, e-magazines, e-newspapers, other internet resources, and e-law journals in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi. This is in agreement with Okiki (2013), who found out that journals, books, the Internet, websites, search engines, e-journals, e-books, reference sources, and e-catalogues were readily available to academics.

Regarding to the question of whether law students are allowed to use mobile phones to access subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library Makurdi, the study reported that law students who are duly registered with the law library are allowed to

utilize their mobile phones in the library to access and use subscribed law library resources while those are not registered with the library are not allowed to enter the library talk more of utilizing their mobile phones to access subscribed library resources in the law library. This is in collaboration with Raphael (2022), who pointed out that students are allowed to use their mobile phones for the purpose of exploring electronic information resources available in their libraries.

On the extent to which law students' use mobile phones to access subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi, the study reveals that majority of the students use it to access other internet resources, e-newspapers and e-law books to a high extent while others use it to access e-law journals and e-law students' theses to a less extent. This agrees with the findings of Chaputulu and

Mulula (2018) that usage of mobile phones to access e-books, e-journals and the library website was high.

In view of the extent of the application of the concept of fair dealing by law students in the use of mobile phones to access, download and re-use subscribed library resources in the BSU law Library Makurdi, the study show that a higher number of law students apply the concept of fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access, download and re-use subscribed library resources such as e-law journals, e-law books and e-law students theses to a high extent while some apply it to a less extent

Finally, the application of the concept of fair dealing by law students' use of mobile phones to access, download, and re-use subscribed law library resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi has a greater impact on their educational achievement and research activities. It also enables them to add value to the original word, line, or portion of the subscribed document accessed and used, and enable them to create new insights and understanding on words, lines or portions of the subscribed document accessed and used through their phones. However, to other law students reported that the application of the concept of fair dealing prevents them from claiming ownership of other people's work

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendation are made

1. Law students should also use mobile phones to access subscribed library resources such as e-statutes and e-magazines to a high extent.
2. Law students should also apply the concept of fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access, download and re-use subscribed library resources such as e-statutes and e-newspapers to a high extent.
3. Law students who do not apply the concept of fair dealing in their use of

mobile phones to access, download and re-use of subscribed legal library resources to claim the ownership of other people's ideas should know that it is legally and academically wrong.

Conclusion

Mobile phones are vital devices in the provision of access to information in general and subscribed legal information resources in particular. In realization of the importance of mobile phones in information access and use, the Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi, subscribed to legal information resources and allows law students to utilize their mobile phones to access and utilize the subscribed resources. However, while the majority of the law students of the Benue State University, Makurdi, in turn apply the concept of fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access, download, and re-use subscribed library resources such as e-law journals, e-law books, and e-law students' theses to a great extent, some apply it to a lesser extent. This has a greater impact on their educational achievement and research activities. The study, therefore, concludes that law students complied with fair dealing in their use of mobile phones to access, download, and re-use subscribed library resources in Benue State University Law Library, Makurdi.

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